

Trajectories of Enslavement at the Atlantic Periphery

Tracing an African Woman in Eighteenth-Century Belarusian-Lithuanian Lands¹

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Working Paper

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to use microhistorical reading of scarce, biased and fragmented sources to reconstruct the largely silent and silenced biography of an African woman in the eighteenth-century Belarusian-Lithuanian lands. Its central figure is Katarzyna, later Katarzyna Rudnicka, who appears only briefly in several archival traces connected with the Radziwiłł household: a diary entry from 1745, a travel diary from 1773–1774, a private letter from 1779, her own petition from 1800, and later pension records. None of these sources was created to preserve her life story. Nevertheless, when read closely and against the grain, they allow us to restore at least a tentative trajectory of displacement, service, dependency, retirement and patronage. By combining microhistory, critical attention to archival silence, and the concept of asymmetrical dependency, the paper suggests a possible way of writing African actors back into Belarusian and Lithuanian history.

Keywords: African presence; erased biographies; archival silence; microhistory; fragmented sources; biased sources; Belarus; Lithuania; Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth; Russian Empire; the Radziwiłłs; Katarzyna Murzynka; Katarzyna Rudnicka; asymmetrical dependency; Black history; eighteenth century; East-Central Europe.

Introduction

We usually imagine the history of Belarus, Lithuania, Poland and Ukraine as a white history, in a racial sense. It feels almost self-evident. So self-evident, in fact, that to question it may sound strange or even uncomfortable.

But if we look more closely at the sources, and also at what has already been noticed by historians, Africans do appear in Belarusian history. Not often, of course. The references are brief, scattered and sometimes rather difficult to interpret, they have usually remained outside the main historical narrative. When such cases are mentioned at all, they are often treated as exotic details, or as something marginal, accidental, maybe even mistaken.

¹ This working paper is based on a presentation delivered at the 11th London Conference on Belarusian Studies, London, 8–9 May 2026.

Still, I would argue that the presence of Africans in the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, and in the Belarusian lands in particular, was not simply an accident. By the early modern period, this region stood on the periphery of a wider globalising world, but it was not outside it. It was connected, indirectly and unevenly, with the Atlantic economy and with wider trans-imperial networks. Through these networks, goods moved between continents. People from these hinterland societies travelled overseas, and, although in much smaller numbers and under very different conditions, Africans came here too.

Sources show that there were people of African descent who came voluntarily and even those of mixed African and European descent who may already have been born here. But in the early modern context, many were brought without choice. Often as children, abducted from their families and trafficked to Europe not for labour, but as what we might call living Baroque decorations.²

This paper is motivated by the double difficulty of reconstructing African lives in the early modern Polish-Lithuanian context. Like many subaltern people, dependent Africans appear in the sources mainly through the eyes, interests, and language of their masters or other dominant actors. Moreover, their lives are even more easily lost, because later scholarship has often not treated these traces as material for individual biography. By attempting to recover one particular life of an African woman, Katarzyna (before 1745 – after 1810), from scarce and biased evidence, this paper explores how microhistorical reading can resist such erasure and make visible both the limits of the sources and the human trajectory hidden within them.

Methods and approaches

Writing such a history, however, is challenging for several reasons. The sources were usually produced by social superiors and are therefore not only fragmentary but also biased, as is typical in the study of subaltern groups. Secondly, race was not yet an established concept, and the terms used to describe those whom we would now call Africans or Black people were unstable and situational. Finally, these dependent Black people do not fit neatly into the established social categories and hierarchies of Polish-Lithuanian society. It is not always clear whether they should be described as slaves, servants, dependants, or in some other way.

For this reason, I approach this material with two conceptual tools. First, instead of trying to assign them a single fixed legal status, I employ the concept of strong asymmetrical dependency. What I mean by this is a relationship in which a master controls access to crucial resources, restricts mobility, and where leaving the relationship would bring serious consequences for the dependent. Such relations are sustained by institutions, sometimes formal, but often informal and not clearly defined.³

Considering the scarcity and biases of the sources, I use a method close to critical fabulation. Reading sources critically against the grain and placing them in context, I try to construct a plausible, though not definitive, narrative.⁴ Thus, I try to reconstruct one forgotten

² Krzysztof Wittels, "Początki afrykańskiej diaspory nad Wisłą," in *Afryka w Warszawie*, ed. Paweł Średziński and Mamadou Diouf (Warszawa: Fundacja „Afryka Inaczej”, 2010).

³ Julia Winnebeck, Ove Sutter, Adrian Hermann, Christoph Antweiler, and Stephan Conermann. "The Analytical Concept of Asymmetrical Dependency." *Journal of Global Slavery* 8, no. 1 (2023): 7-8.

⁴ Saidiya Hartman, "Venus in Two Acts," *Small Axe* 12, no. 2 (2008): 11.

life trajectory: of an African woman, Katarzyna Murzynka, who lived mostly in the Belarusian lands in the eighteenth century.

Note on sources, translation and terminology

This text is a working paper based on a conference presentation and presents preliminary findings from an ongoing research project. Its aim is to make the source constellation visible and to test a possible microhistorical reconstruction, rather than to offer a definitive biography.

Unless otherwise indicated, all translations from archival and manuscript sources are my own. In the main text, I use contemporary forms of personal and place names where this helps readability, while preserving the original Polish or other historical forms in quoted source passages and archival references.

The terminology used in the sources is not neutral. Historical Polish terms such as *Murzyn* and *Murzynka* are today contested and may be perceived as racially offensive. In this paper, I use them only when they appear in the sources or when their use is necessary for scholarly clarity. Where translation is needed, I usually render *Murzyn* and *Murzynka* as “Moor” and “Mooress”, not as my own descriptive terms, but as historically approximate equivalents that preserve the early modern and courtly character of the language. Whenever possible, I also provide the original term in brackets or discuss it directly.

Master’s diary: possible origins

So, where did Katarzyna come from? On December 8, 1745, Michał Kazimierz Radziwiłł “Rybeńko” noted in his diary that a Kalmyk woman, Maura, and Katarzyna the Mooress converted from the Orthodox faith to Catholicism. This brief entry also gives us a few clues about an earlier stage in their forced and tangled life trajectories:

8 December. In the morning we confessed and took communion — my wife and I, and [also] a Kalmyk woman, Maura, who converted today from the Schismatic [Orthodox] faith to the Catholic faith. The same was to be done today in Nieśwież by Katarzyna Murzynka [Mooress], these being two girls who [had served] in the household of the Grand Duchess of Muscovy, Anna of the House of Mecklenburg, wife of Duke of Brunswick, mother of Tsar Jan [Ivan] when they were [overthrown?], alias deposed, by Elizabeth, the current Tsaritsa of Russia, and taken into captivity; these two maids dispatched with the people of Duke of Brunswick to Germany, remained with my wife and serve at her chamber [?].⁵

But how did this African girl arrive in Russia in the first place? If judged against wider patterns of African trafficking to Europe, a West African origin would be plausible. Yet Katarzyna’s earlier connection with Russia also leaves open another route, possibly through eastern diplomatic and courtly networks. At this time, Russia maintained diplomatic relations

⁵ Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/6/II-80a, *Kopia diariusza Michała Kazimierza Radziwiłła „Rybeńko” (1702–1762), hetmana wielkiego litewskiego i wojewody wileńskiego, z zapiskami z lat [1702], 1719–1761*, pp. 1398–1399. See the original in Appendix 1.

with Persia, and embassies brought enslaved Africans, among other gifts. In 1736, for example, alongside jewels, silks and elephants, 9 Moors and Mooresses were presented. In 1741, another embassy followed, however, this time, researchers did not mention Africans.⁶ So we cannot be certain, but an eastern route, possibly from East Africa through Iran, remains also plausible.

We do not know the girl's original name, ethnic or social belonging, language, or faith – these details were either unknown to her master or likely irrelevant. What the sources show us instead is a sequence of conversions and identity rewritings through which she gradually became Katarzyna Murzynka.

A Mistress's Diary: African Companions

The next mention of her comes from 1773, in the travel diary of Teofila Konstancja Morawska, born Radziwiłł, the daughter of "Rybeńko". Teofila was a rather unconventional woman. She had married, against expectations, to a modest junior officer, Ignacy Morawski and lived a rather modest life in Bielica manor in Lida county, while nevertheless maintaining close ties with her powerful family.⁷

In 1773–1774, she travelled abroad to visit her exiled brother Karol Stanisław Radziwiłł "Panie Kochanku" and other relatives. During a European journey, she briefly noted that she was accompanied by a small staff, including Katarzyna Murzynka and Wojciech.⁸ Probably, Katarzyna kept service with this daughter of her former masters.

This short diary remark has had a revealing afterlife. The contemporary editor of the diary publication did not believe his eyes that Katarzyna could be a *Murzynka*, a Mooress, even though it is clearly written in the manuscript. Instead, the word was altered into the plausible Polish surname *Muszynka*.⁹ This is a case of unintended retrospective erasure. Even when Africans clearly appear in sources, historians may fail to recognise them because of the preconception of the obvious and natural whiteness of the past. Such misreadings contribute to the invisibility of these already barely visible individuals.

Wojciech, mentioned alongside Katarzyna, was also of African origin. He belonged to a group of 12 African children purchased in London in 1752 by Hieronim Florian Radziwiłł for theatrical training in the Radziwiłł court. Most did not succeed, but a few did, and Wojciech played in performances for several years.¹⁰ However, despite his talents, at some point, he ended up as an attendant of Teofila in a rural manor house. Interestingly, he is not described in racial terms in this context. This reflects the fact that racial categorisation was not always consistent or central in these regions. Blackness was visible, but not always formally defined.

⁶ Nigar Gozalova, "Posol'stvo Nadir Shakha Afshara k russkomu dvoru (1739–1742)," *Karavan* (2020).

⁷ Bogdan Rok, "Listy Teofili z Radziwiłłów Morawskiej — przykład staropolskiej epistolografii kobiecej," in *Kobiece kręgi korespondencyjne w XVII–XIX wieku*, ed. Bożena Popiołek, Urszula Kicińska and Agnieszka Słaby (Warszawa, 2016), 188–89.

⁸ Teofila Konstancja z Radziwiłłów Morawska, *Diariusz podróży zagranicę Teofili Konstancji z Radziwiłłów generalowej Ignacowej Morawskiej w latach 1773–1774*, Biblioteka Uniwersytecka w Wilnie, MS F3-1149, p. 30, digital facsimile, Zenodo 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11263460>.

⁹ Teofila Konstancja z Radziwiłłów Morawska, *Diariusz podróży europejskiej w latach 1773–1774*, wstęp i oprac. Bogdan Rok, (Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Wrocławskiego, 2002), 60.

¹⁰ Irena Bieńkowska, *Muzyka na dworze księcia Hieronima Floriana Radziwiłła* (Warszawa: Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2013), 245–260, 410.

Playful letter: gendered racism

Katarzyna likely spent much of her life in Bielica, but she also seems to have travelled with her mistress within aristocratic social networks, especially to assemblies in Vilnius, Warsaw, Hrodna.¹¹

In 1779, Teofila wrote a letter to her brother Karol Stanisław Radziwiłł "Panie Kochanku", inviting him to Vilnius for the carnival season.

At the masquerade, there was a most peculiar skirmish. Two young ladies, Horodeńska and Krajewska, both beauties, came to blows, slapping each other in the face over who should have first place in the dance, and the quarrel is still going on. Who knows, perhaps it may come to a duel. But upon my word, they are pretty. Your Princely Grace could surely reconcile them with that weapon of yours you carry beneath your belt. Do take pity and come to Vilnius for the next four Sundays, there would be young ladies enough, and one might even be found for Secretary Bernatowicz, at least my Mooress Kasia.¹²

This remark about Kasia (Katarzyna) can be read in different ways. On the one hand, it may reflect racist irony in the modern sense: Teofila compares beautiful young noblewomen to a dark-skinned aged woman of about fifty, who evidently did not conform to the ideals of youth and beauty of that society. However, it may also be a much grimmer hint, pointing to the sexual exploitation that often targeted vulnerable servant maids, and perhaps especially someone as exoticised and unprotected as she was. Despite the sexualisation of the Black female body being a noticeable trend in European discourse since the Middle Ages,¹³ this issue is especially invisible in Belarusian sources – but not necessarily absent.

Katarzyna's petition: reconstructing subaltern voice

The most extensive and unique source on Katarzyna dates from 1800, after the collapse of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, when, without ever leaving her place of residence, she once again found herself a subject of the Russian Empire. The document is a petition addressed to Michał Hieronim Radziwiłł, then head of the Radziwiłł estates. Uniquely, it offers a rare opportunity to attempt a reconstruction of Katarzyna's own voice and perspective, however mediated by the conventions of petitionary writing.

*Most Illustrious Prince, my Lord and Benefactor,
With great hesitation, I dare through this letter to embrace and kiss the feet of His Illustrious Highness, the Prince, my Lord and Benefactor, reminding him of me after three years, and of the promised favor, namely the granting of several hundred zlotys to me, an orphan-foreigner, who from young years in the house of His Illustrious Highness the Princes raised and served [or: deserved]. Now I remain in a very miserable state of*

¹¹ Rok, "Listy Teofili z Radziwiłłów Morawskiej," 189.

¹² Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/5/10006-2, *Morawska Teofila z ks. Radziwiłłów*, p. 58.

¹³ Noémie Ndiaye, *Scripts of Blackness: Early Modern Performance Culture and the Making of Race*, ed. Geraldine Heng and Ayanna Thompson (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2022), 106–8.

*poverty, so that I have no means even for my living, nor anything with which to repair the empty small townhouse that I hold in Vilnius for life. If His Illustrious Highness, Prince, my Lord and Benefactor, would consider some way by which I might have something to live on, and would give orders for the repair of the townhouse, or assign money for its restoration, and now also, out of special regard and mercy, would help and support me with a few red zlotys [ducats], God will reward this a hundredfold, and I will, for the whole course of my life, never stop praying and wishing the longest years and prosperity, declaring at the feet my most dutiful respect to the Illustrious Prince, my Lord and Benefactor,
faithful servant
and most humble supplicant,
Katarzyna Rudnicka, Mooress [Arapka] and Orphan
in Bielica, in the year 1800,
on the 7th day of August.¹⁴*

This short petition is dense with details that help to reconstruct Katarzyna's position, her circumstances, and the way her case was framed. I focus here on just a few of them.

First, Katarzyna appears here for the only time with a surname — Rudnicka. This is quite unusual for someone of her status. We do not know whether she acquired it through marriage, or whether this reflects the growing bureaucratic requirements of the Russian administration. However, it underlines her subjectivity and independent status.

Another unusual detail is that Katarzyna refers to herself using the Russian term *Arapka*. It may reflect her earlier identification in Russia, which remained with her throughout her life. Or it may be linked to the administrative context, since she was now dealing with Russian-speaking officials. It is also possible that, in this context, the term *Murzyn* functioned not only as an ethnic or racial designation, but also as a courtly service role. In this sense, it may have worked somewhat like terms such as *hajduk* or *Cossack*, which in noble household contexts did not always refer to actual Hungarian or Cossack origin, but could denote stylised forms of service functions, dress and armour or status. Thus, by calling herself *Arapka*, she may have been distancing herself from her former servant *Murzyn* status.

She also refers to herself as an orphan. This seems to be a particularly meaningful self-description. In the sources I have consulted, such Africans are not explicitly labelled as *niewolnicy*, or slaves. This case shows that their status could be described in a paternalistic manner, where they could be treated as minor, dependent members of the household. This implied an expectation of lifelong gratitude and service, often without formal remuneration. Indeed, such Africans rarely appear in salary records and, unlike many other servants, did not accumulate wealth even after long service. Even in old age or retirement, they remained dependent on the goodwill and material support of their former patrons. At the same time, this dependency also seems to have created an expectation, or perhaps a claim, that patrons owed them protection and care. This offers an important clue to how the status and identity of such

¹⁴ Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/R 95, *Rudnicka Katarzyna, murzynka. Prośba o względy, kwity na dożywotnią pensję*, pp. 1–2. See the original in Appendix 2.

individuals were shaped within noble households, especially when they entered them as children.

Pension receipts: happy end?

The petition appears to have been successful. Records show that Katarzyna received a pension until 1810.¹⁵ She seems to have passed away around that time, at an advanced age, probably close to eighty. In this respect, her life trajectory was unusually well preserved and, perhaps, more protected than those of many other African servants, whose lives were often short, isolated, and marked by deep dependency. Many of them seem to have died alone, from harsh climate and diseases, without family, property, or real autonomy, leaving behind only a few lines in their masters' paperwork. Katarzyna's case, by contrast, allows us to see not only dependency and vulnerability, but also endurance, a claim to patronage, and the fragile possibility of recognition after a long life of service.

Interestingly, Jean Lapierre, the official appearing in this pension receipt, was also a person of African, or, more likely, Afro-Caribbean descent. He had served Tadeusz Kościuszko, later entered the service of the Radziwiłłs as an attendant, and went on to make a remarkable career. He became a *marszałek*, that is, a chamberlain of the Radziwiłł household, a member of a Masonic lodge, and eventually even a landowner.¹⁶

Lapierre represents, in a way, a different type of Black presence in this region. By the late eighteenth century, we can observe the emergence of a group of free African servants. They often spoke several European languages, were skilled in their roles, and were on the move between different aristocratic households and even countries. In this document, then, quite symbolically, we see a kind of meeting point between these two groups of Africans at the margins of the Atlantic world.

Conclusion

The case of Katarzyna may suggest that the history of hinterland East-Central Europe was more deeply entangled in global processes than is usually assumed, including slavery and intercontinental human mobility.

Even in the absence of a clearly defined system of chattel slavery, we can still observe forms of coercion and dependency that shaped the lives of such individuals. Katarzyna's trajectory, from probable abduction in childhood to lifelong service in elite households, demonstrates objectification, repeated displacement, and attempts to reshape and control identity. At the same time, her case also shows that these conditions were not entirely static. Despite isolation and limited access to social and material resources, she appears to have developed certain strategies of adaptation. Her later petition may indicate a sense of dignity and an ability to navigate the patronage system of a hierarchical society, rather than simple passive acceptance.

¹⁵ Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/K 50, *Osoby w kolejności alfabetycznej wg nazwisk: Katarzyna, murzynka. Asygnacje na zasługi*. 1804–1808, pp. 1–4; Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/R 95, *Osoby w kolejności alfabetycznej wg nazwisk: Rudnicka Katarzyna, murzynka. Prośba o względy, kwity na dożywotnią pensję*, 1800–1810, pp. 3–4.

¹⁶ Krzysztof Wittels, "Początki afrykańskiej diaspory nad Wisłą," in *Afryka w Warszawie*, ed. Paweł Średziński and Mamadou Diouf (Warszawa: Fundacja „Afryka Inaczej”, 2010), 27–29.

The case of Katarzyna is a relatively well-documented example of an African woman living in dependency in Polish-Lithuanian society. The surviving sources do not allow a full biography, but they make possible a cautious and relatively consistent reconstruction of her life trajectory. Through them, we can approach several aspects of her experience: conversion, personal status, mobility across political and social borders, relations with masters and mediators, and even hints of how she may have understood her own position. At the same time, the limits of this reconstruction remain clear. Katarzyna appears mainly through the attention, gaze, language and interventions of others. Moreover, the problem is not only the bias of the sources themselves. Her case is visible in the archives, but it has not been properly integrated into scholarship, partly because African lives have long seemed not to belong to the history of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth. This creates a form of unintended silencing. The task of the researcher is therefore not only to find such sources and read them against their biases, but also to ask questions that allow these lives to become visible in the first place.

The relative invisibility of Africans in the history of Belarus and East-Central Europe more broadly seems to result not primarily from the scarcity of sources, but also from the limits of our historical perspective — from what we expect to see, and what we are prepared to recognise as part of this history.

LITERATURE

Archival and Manuscript Sources

Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/6/II-80a. *Kopia diariusza Michała Kazimierza Radziwiłła „Rybeńko” (1702–1762), hetmana wielkiego litewskiego i wojewody wileńskiego, z zapiskami z lat [1702], 1719–1761.*

Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/5/10006-2. *Morawska Teofila z ks. Radziwiłłów. 1778–1790.*

Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/K 50. *Katarzyna, murzynka. Asygnacje na zasługi. 1804–1808.*

Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/R 95. *Osoby w kolejności alfabetycznej wg nazwisk: Rudnicka Katarzyna, murzynka. Prośba o względy, kwity na dożywotnią pensję, 1800–1810.*

Morawska, Teofila Konstancja z Radziwiłłów. *Diariusz podróży zagranicę Teofili Konstancji z Radziwiłłów generalowej Ignacowej Morawskiej w latach 1773–1774.* Manuscript. Biblioteka Uniwersytecka w Wilnie, MS F3-1149. Digital facsimile. Zenodo, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11263460>.

Published Sources and Scholarship

Bieńkowska, Irena. *Muzyka na dworze księcia Hieronima Floriana Radziwiłła.* Warszawa: Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, 2013.

Gozalova, Nigar. “Posol’stvo Nadir Shakha Afshara k russkomu dvoru (1739–1742).” *Karavan* no. 82 (2020): 16–38.

Hartman, Saidiya. “Venus in Two Acts.” *Small Axe* 12, no. 2 (2008): 1–14.

Morawska, Teofila Konstancja z Radziwiłłów. *Diariusz podróży europejskiej w latach 1773–1774.* Edited and introduced by Bogdan Rok. Wrocław: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Wrocławskiego, 2002.

Ndiaye, Noémie. *Scripts of Blackness: Early Modern Performance Culture and the Making of Race.* Edited by Geraldine Heng and Ayanna Thompson. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.9783/9781512822649>.

Rok, Bogdan. “Listy Teofili z Radziwiłłów Morawskiej — przykład staropolskiej epistolografii kobiecej.” In *Kobiece kręgi korespondencyjne w XVII–XIX wieku*, edited by Bożena Popiołek, Urszula Kicińska and Agnieszka Słaby, 187–199. Warszawa, 2016.

Winnebeck, Julia, Ove Sutter, Adrian Hermann, Christoph Antweiler and Stephan Conermann. “The Analytical Concept of Asymmetrical Dependency.” *Journal of Global Slavery* 8, no. 1 (2023): 1–59.

Wittels, Krzysztof. “Początki afrykańskiej diaspory nad Wisłą.” In *Afryka w Warszawie*, edited by Paweł Średziński and Mamadou Diouf, 13–31. Warszawa: Fundacja „Afryka Inaczej”, 2010.

APPENDIX

Selected Archival Sources

Note. The following appendix provides selected scans and transcriptions of the two central archival documents discussed in the paper. English translations are quoted in the main text. The transcription of the 1745 diary entry is accompanied by cropped digital images made available through Szukaj w Archiwach. The transcription of the 1800 petition is based on photographs taken by the author in the Scientific Reading Room of AGAD; the photographs are not reproduced here. The transcriptions preserve original spelling, capitalisation and punctuation as far as possible. Uncertain readings are marked in square brackets.

Appendix 1. Michał Kazimierz Radziwiłł's diary, 8 December 1745

Archival reference: Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/6/II-80a, *Kopia diariusza Michała Kazimierza Radziwiłła „Rybeńko” (1702–1762), hetmana wielkiego litewskiego i wojewody wileńskiego, z zapiskami z lat [1702], 1719–1761, pp. 1398–1399.*

Online access: <https://www.szukajwarchiwach.gov.pl/skan/-/skan/947d02f239876e50798be0c574b4214981e14a05908bec327150eaa5bdd53ec1>, accessed 17 June 2026.

Source type: Diary entry.

English translation: quoted in the main text, section “Master’s diary: possible origins”.

Fig. A1. Fig. A1. Michał Kazimierz Radziwiłł's diary, entry of 8 December 1745, detail from p. 1398. AGAD, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, sygn. II-80a (1/354/0/6/II-80a). Digital image via Szukaj w Archiwach; cropped by the author.

Fig. A2. Michał Kazimierz Radziwiłł's diary, entry of 8 December 1745, detail from p. 1399. AGAD, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, sygn. II-80a (1/354/0/6/II-80a). Digital image via Szukaj w Archiwach; cropped by the author.

[p. 1398] 8 Xbris z Rana Spowiadaliśmy się Y Kommunikowaliśmy się z Żoną moją. Y Kałmuczką Maurę którą Dziś Publicznie z Schyzmatycznej na Wiarę Katolicką rewolowała, toż samo miała dziś w Nieświeżu Katharzyna Murzynka uczynić, iż to Dwie Dziewki które u Wielkiej Xiężny Moskiewskiej Anny z Domu Mekleburgskiej a żony Xięcia **Prunswickiego** Matki Cara Jana, jak tedy te Panstwo byli zmuzulwowani [?] alias zrzuceni przez Elzbięte terażniejszą Carową Rosyi I w niewolę pobrani te Dwie Niewiasty Wyprawione z Ludźmi Xięcia Prunswickiego do Niemiec [p. 1399] do Niemiec Zostały u Żoney moiej Y Służą podwierne [?].

Appendix 2. Katarzyna Rudnicka's petition, 7 August 1800

Archival reference: Archiwum Główne Akt Dawnych, Archiwum Warszawskie Radziwiłłów, 1/354/0/21/R 95, *Osoby w kolejności alfabetycznej wg nazwisk: Rudnicka Katarzyna, murzynka. Prośba o względy, kwity na dożywotnią pensję*, 1800–1810, pp. 1–2.

Transcription basis: photographs taken by the author in the Scientific Reading Room of AGAD; images not reproduced.

Source type: Petition.

English translation: quoted in the main text, section “Katarzyna's petition: reconstructing subaltern voice”.

[p. 2]

Memoryał

Jasnie Oświeconemu Xięciu JPanu

Radziwiłłowi

Woiewodzie Wileńskiemu

Opiekunowi, y Kawalerowi Orderów wielu

od Arapki cudzo Ziemki u Nóg

podaięc

[Katarzyna] Rudnicka Murzynka

[p. 1]

Jasnie Oświecony Mości Xiąże Panie y Dobrodziēju

Z Wielką nieśmiałością odważam się tym pismem ucisnąć i ucałować Nogi JO. Xcia Pana y Dobrodzieia, przypominaięc się od Lat trzech, przyobięcanych okazania względów, wyznaczenia

kilkasett złotych, jako Sierocie Cudzoziemce, z młodych Lat w Domie JO. Xiążąt wyhodowaną, zasłużoną, teraz bardzo w mizernym zostaię ubóstwa stanie, że I do Życia niemam sposobności, ani też czym wyreperować Kamieniczkę pusto maiąc w Wilnie do Żywocie. Obmyśliwsz JO. msc Xiąże Panie y Dobrodzieju tę sposobność, bym mogła zacząć żyć, I wydasz rozkazy reperowania Kamienicy, lub za Assygnuiąc daniem Pieniędzy na poprawę Oney, A mnie teraz prze osobliwszy uzgląd i miłosierdzie opatrzycz wspomozesz kilku Czerwonemi Złotemi, Bóg za to stokrotnie nagrodzi, a Ja ciągniem Życia prosić nie przestanię w życzeniu Lat naydłuższych, pomyślności wszelkich wyznaiąca u Nóg nay powiniejszego Uszanowania

Oświeconego Xięcia Pana
y Dobrodzięja wierna Sługa
y nayunięsza Podnoszka
Katarzyna Rudnicka Arapka i Sierota

w Bielicy 1800 Ro[ku]
Dnia 7 Augusta.